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- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
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- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
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- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
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MUNDARIJA

INNOVATSION SIYOSATNI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI – OLIY TA'LIM TRANSFORMATSIYASI, RAQAMLI MODERNIZATSIYA VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH OMILLARI.....	13
Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich	
O'ZBEKISTON YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHI: ZARURAT, MAQSADI VA AYRIM MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLAR	16
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna	
FAN, TA'LIM VA ISHLAB CHIQRISHDAGI SO'NGGI TENDENSIYALAR VA INNOVATSIYALAR	25
To'ychiyev Olimjon Alijonovich	
QURILISH TASHKILOTLARIDA KREDITGA LAYOQATLILIKNI BAHOLASHNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH	30
Mavlanov Normo'min Normamatovich	
BUDJET TASHKILOTLARIDA DAVLAT XARIDLARINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISHDA ELEKTRON SAVDOLARNING AHAMIYATI.....	37
Turabov Sarvar Abdumalikovich	
O'ZBEKISTONNI MINTAQAVIY TA'LIM VA ILM-FAN HABIGA AYLANTIRISHNING ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI	41
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li	
HUDUDIY RIVOJLANISH STRATEGIYALARIGA INNOVATSION KOMPONENTLARNI INTEGRATSIYA QILISH USULLARI	46
Muminov Fazliddin Xusniddin o'g'li	
OROL DENGIZI MEROSI: EKOLOGIK FOJIANI BARQAROR EKOTURIZM IMKONIYATLARIGA AYLANTIRISH	52
Zufarova Nozima	
KORXONALARNING YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYASINI ISHLAB CHIQISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	60
Ergashxodjayeva Shaxnoza Djasurovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ISHCHI KUCHI BOZORINING TAKRORIY AMAL QILISHINING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	66
Mamaraximov B.E.	
BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR VA MOLIYAVIY INSTRUMENTLARDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI GAROV DIVERSIFIKATSIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	70
Xolbozorov Husniddin Norbek o'g'li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA MARKETINGNING INNOVATSION KONSEPSIYALARI.....	76
Jumayev Olimjon Sadulloevich, Axmedova Shoxsanam Sindbod qizi	
SAVDO KORXONALARIDA EKOLOGIK MAHSULOTLARNI TARG'IB QILISH VA SOTISHNI RAG'BATLANTIRISH USULLARI	84
Jalalova Dildora Jamolovna	
DIRECTIONS OF FORMING AND PROVIDING A COMPETITIVE EXPORT-ORIENTED ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	87
Asatullaev Khurshid Sunatullaevich, Nasirxodjaeva Dilafruz Sabitkhanovna, Abdullayeva Madina Kamilovna	
FROM SCIENCE TO BUSINESS: HOW UNIVERSITIES STIMULATE INNOVATION	94
Prof. A. Bobozhonov, Prof. A.M. Shatre, Assoc. Prof. V. Kirilova Vladimirova, prof. R.Kh. Karlibaeva	
PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF GREEN TECHNOLOGIES IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON ADVANCED INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE	100
Otamuratov Sarvar	
SPECIFIC FEATURES OF MIGRATION FROM UZBEKISTAN AND PROSPECTS FOR ORGANIZATIONAL IMPROVEMENT	105
Sabirova Lola Shavkatovna, Shaislamova Nargiza Kabilovna	

KORXONA BARQAROR AXBOROT TIZIMINI YARATISH QIYINCHILIKLARI.....	112
Abidov Abdujabbar Abduxamidovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI FAOLIYATIGA FOIZ RISKINING TA'SIRI VA ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	119
Isakov.J.Ya	
CREATION OF A MECHANISM FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND INTRODUCTION OF A MODEL OF COMPLETE TRANSITION TO THE NETZERO ENERGY SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN	127
Makhmudova Guljakhon N., Gulomova Nigora Farxadovna	
УСИЛЕНИЕ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОГО МЕХАНИЗМА НА СТОИМОСТНУЮ ОЦЕНКУ ОСНОВНЫХ ФАКТОРОВ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА.....	133
Алишер Расулев, Сергей Воронин	
РОЛЬ ФИНАНСОВОЙ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ В РАЗВИТИИ МАЛОГО И СРЕДНЕГО ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА: ПЕРСПЕКТИВА И ПРИКЛАДНЫЕ РЕШЕНИЯ ДЛЯ ИХ ПЕРЕХОДА К МСФО.....	143
Эргашева Шахло Тургуновна	
DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMIC ACTIVITY UNDER DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	151
Boburjon Vafoev	
ENERGETIKA TIZIMIDAGI KORXONALAR MOLIYAVIY HOLATINING TAHLILI.....	157
Matnazar Yusupovich Raximov	
АСПЕКТЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЕМ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ.....	162
Очилова Хилола Фармоновна	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLAR.....	167
Abdullayev Suyun Artikovich	
THE INTERCONNECTION BETWEEN DIGITAL LEARNING PLATFORMS AND THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	171
Kuchkarov Takhir Safarovich, Kholmonov Shodiyor Karshiboyevich	
BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMI VA XUSUSIY SEKTORNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA YANGI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA BANK FAOLIYATINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI	174
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich	
РАЗВИТИЕ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА В РАМКАХ ПЕРСПЕКТИВ ВСТУПЛЕНИЯ ВО ВСЕМИРНУЮ ТОРГОВУЮ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЮ	180
У.А.Юлдашева	
ЗЕЛЕННЫЕ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛИ - ПУТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЕННОГО РОСТА В РАМКАХ УСТОЙЧИВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	185
Дехканова Наргиза Шарифовна	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АУДИТ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	192
Ходжаева М.Х.	
TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA AHOLINING MOLIYAVIY SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	199
Akbarova Barno Shuxratovna	
SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH TOURISM UNDER THE GREEN ECONOMY FRAMEWORK	204
Jumayev Akbar Mahmudovich	
МАКРОИQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA BANK TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	210
Erkinxojiyev Ismoiljon Ikromjon o'g'li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA MINTAQAVIY SANOAT KORXONALARIDA KORPORATIV MADANIYATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....	216
Matrizayeva Dilaram Yusupbayevna	
UZBEKISTAN AT THE CROSSROADS OF HISTORY AND GREEN INNOVATION: FROM THE GREAT SILK ROAD TO A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE	220
Avalova Gulshod Murodullayevna	

ГЛАВНЫЕ ВЕКТОРЫ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ ПО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЮ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	226
Абдуллаева М.К.	
ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT IN THE INDUSTRIAL CLUSTERS SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN: MODERN TRENDS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS.....	233
Kholikova Rukhsora Sanjarovna	
HUDUDDAGI KICHIK BIZNESNING SAMARALI TARKIBIY TUZILMASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA MUTASSADI TASHKILOTLARNING O'ZARO UYG'UN HARAKATINI TASHKIL ETISH.....	239
Sharipov Kuvondik Baxtiyorovich	
BUSINESS ANALYTICS IN HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE: LESSONS FROM THE INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION TO THE DIGITAL AGE	246
Burhanova Sabo Tulanovna	
"COST ENGINEERING"NING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA UNI IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHDAGI O'RNI.....	252
Zaynitdinova Umida Djalalovna	
FEATURES AND WAYS OF FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	256
Kobilov Alisher, Majidova Irodahon	
ПИЩЕВАЯ ИНДУСТРИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: АГРАРНЫЙ ИМПУЛЬС, ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ И ЦЕНОВАЯ КОНЪЮНКТУРА.....	263
Юлдашев Голибжон Тургунович, Элдорбеков Гофурбек Искандарбек угли	
INCOME INEQUALITY AND MACROECONOMIC DETERMINANTS IN UZBEKISTAN: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS	273
Muhammad Eid Balbaa, Marina Sagatovna Abdurashidova	
РЫНОК ТРУДА В УСЛОВИЯХ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	276
Амирджанова Ситора Суннат кизи	
EKOLOGIK QO'RIQXONALARDA MONITORING JARAYONLARINING IQTISODIY VA TASHKILIY ANAMIYATI.....	282
Homidov Hamdam Hasan o'g'li	
ГАРМОНИЗАЦИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН В СООТВЕТСТВИИ С МСФО	288
Абдужалилова Дилноз Абдусаттаровна	
SUSTAINABLE TOURISM AND BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION: CASE OF UZBEKISTAN WITHIN THE UNESCO WORLD HERITAGE FRAMEWORK.....	294
Yuldasheva Dilnoza Ulugbekovna	
ПРАКТИЧЕСКОЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ НЕЙРОМАРКЕТИНГА НА МАРКЕТПЛЕЙСАХ (WILDBERRIES, UZUM MARKET, ЯНДЕКС МАРКЕТ)	300
Юлдашев Жамшид Абрарович	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА КАК СТИМУЛ РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ТРУДА УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	309
Шаюсупова Наргиза Тургуновна	
GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANISHI O'ZBEKISTONNING XALQARO SAVDOSIGA VA IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGIGA TAHDID SIFATIDA.....	315
Mamatov Mamajan Ahmadjonovich	
SUG'URTA TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH VA INNOVATSION SUG'URTA MAHSULOTLARINI JORIY QILISH MASALALARI	321
Xalikulova Gulzada Tadjimuratovna	
O'ZBEKISTON OZIQ-OVQAT BOZORIDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI BARQAROR ISTE'MOLNI RAG'BATLANTIRISH	333
Eshmatov Sanjar Azimqulovich	
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В РАЗНЫХ ОТРАСЛЯХ ЭКОНОМИКИ: ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЙ ОПЫТ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ПРАКТИКА	337
Назарова Ра'но Рустамовна, Мусаева Гавхар Ахматжон кизи	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTDA MEHNAT BOZORI: O'ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	343
Homidjonov Fozilxon Umarxon o'g'li, Haydarov Kamoliddin Baratovich	

GREEN INVESTMENT: PATHWAYS TOWARD A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE.....	348
Odilova Sitora Sayfitdin kizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA O'ZBEKISTON SANOAT KORXONALARIDA MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	351
Kutbitdinova Mohigul Inoyatovna	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATIDA YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRI	356
Metyakubov Azamat Djumanazarovich	
ELEKTR SANOAT KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA MARKETING VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	361
Tursunxo'jayev Sardor Jamoliddin o'g'li	
УЧЕТ ЗАТРАТ И МЕТОДЫ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ СЕБЕСТОИМОСТИ ПРОДУКЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ	368
Махкамова Саида Гайратовна	
MILLIY HISOBLAR TIZIMIDA INTELLEKTUAL MULK MAHSULOTLARINI MAKROIQTISODIY DARAJADA HISOBGA OLISHNING METODOLOGIK ASOSI.....	375
Sunnatov Muxtor Ne'matovich	
RENEWABLE ENERGY AND MACROECONOMIC STABILITY IN CENTRAL ASIA: PATHWAYS WITHIN THE GREEN ECONOMY	382
Khabibullo Abdullaev	
JAHON SUG'URTA AMALIYOTI ASOSIDA O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA BOZORIDA YANGI RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	387
Abdimovminova Saodat Taxirjonovna	
INTEGRATING DATA SCIENCE INTO GREEN FINANCING AND ECO-INNOVATIONS: ACHIEVING THE GOALS OF UZBEKISTAN-2030	397
Norboev Odil Abraevich, Kungratov Ilmurod Kuzibay ugli	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SANOAT ISHLAB CHIQRISHINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASH AMALIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	404
Olimov Maqsudjon Komiljon o'g'li	
СОЗДАНИЕ ЗЕЛЕННОГО ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОГО КОРИДОРА В ЕВРОПУ: РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА, КАЗАХСТАНА И УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	411
Лала Гамидова Адиль, Арзуман Гусейнов Айдын	
MAHALLA TIZIMIDA AHOLINI OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARIGA BO'LGAN ISTE'MOL TALABLARI MODEL.....	419
S. Qulmatova	
AHOLI ICHKI MIGRATSIYASINING MEHNAT BOZORIGA TA'SIRINI STATISTIK O'RGANISH	427
Mirolimov Mirislom Mirshokir o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BANK TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH TENDENSIYALARI VA MUAMMOLARI	434
Jumaniyozova Mukaddas Yuldashevna	
ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ФИНАНСЫ: ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ ТРЕНДЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	438
Фаттахова Муниса	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI SOHASI FAOLIYATINI DAVLAT TOMONIDAN MUVOFIQLASHTIRISH VA BOSHQARISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	444
Tuxtamishev Shodimurod Qurbonboyevich	
MARKETING TADQIQOTLARI ASOSIDA MEVA-SABZAVOT MAHSULOTLARI EKSPORT SALONIYATINI OSHIRISH.....	452
Xojiyev Elshod Yoqub o'g'li	
СПОСОБЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ НАУЧНЫМИ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯМИ В ЦЕЛЯХ ПЕРЕХОДА НА РАЗРАБОТКУ ЗЕЛЕННЫХ ИННОВАЦИЙ	459
Юдаков Александр Андреевич	
O'ZBEKISTONNI JAHON SAVDO TASHKILOTIGA A'ZO BO'LISHINING OZIQ-OVQAT XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHGA TA'SIRI.....	466
Axmedova N.A.	

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA KLASTERLAR FAOLIYATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY MEKANIZMI	471
<i>Sherkulov Shohruh Erkin o'g'li</i>	
DEVELOPMENT SCENARIOS OF UZBEKISTAN'S ACTIVE LABOR FORCE UNTIL 2030 AND THEIR ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS.....	476
<i>Ganiev Bakhtiyor Zulfikor ugli, Rakhmonov Bekzod Sharibjon ugli</i>	
РАЗВИТИЕ ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ КАК ФАКТОР СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ ЖЕНЩИН В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	481
<i>Дониерова Фотимабону Алишер кизи</i>	
YASHIL ENERGETIKA VA UNING IQTISODIY TARAQQIYOTDAGI O'RNI	488
<i>Babadjanova Malika Ruzimova</i>	
BENCHMARKING IN THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY: STRATEGIES FOR SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVENESS	492
<i>Abdurashidova Nigora</i>	
УЗБЕКИСТАН СТРЕМИТСЯ К УСТОЙЧИВОМУ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОМУ РОСТУ, ВНЕДРЯЯ ПРИНЦИПЫ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ» ЭКОНОМИКИ	498
<i>Сагдуллаева Гулнора Ботыровна</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN KOMPANIYALARNING GLOBAL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	502
<i>Sharipov Ixtiyor Baxtiyorovich</i>	
ZAIF BANDLIKDAN UNUMLI BANDLIK SARI TRANSFORMATSIYA: O'ZINI O'ZI BAND QILISH	507
<i>Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich</i>	
ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМАЯ ЭНЕРГИЯ В ГЛОБАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ: ТЕКУЩИЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И БУДУЩЕЕ РАЗВИТИЕ.....	514
<i>Меҳрибан Самедова Тофик</i>	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING MEHNAT UNUMDORLIGINI OSHIRISHGA TA'SIRI.....	521
<i>Zafar Alisherovich Mamadiev, Nodira Isametdinovna Xasanxonova</i>	
SAVDO KORXONALARIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI XALQARO STANDARTLARGA INTEGRATSIYA QILISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	526
<i>Ablazov Lazizbek Abdiquosimovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING TRANSFORMATSIYASI JARAYONINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	530
<i>Ziyadullaev Z.</i>	
TO'LOV TIZIMI KONSEPTUAL MODELINING SHAKLLANISH TAMOYILLARI.....	537
<i>Toshniyozov Sherali Kamoliddinovich</i>	
STAFF PERFORMANCE EVALUATION BASED ON KPI SYSTEM INDICATORS.....	546
<i>Rakhmatullaeva Shakhnoza Khamidovna, Sadriddinova Sevinchkhon</i>	
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL ECONOMIC TRENDS	555
<i>Svetlana Yurievna Shatokhina</i>	
MILLIY TARBIYA OMILLARI VA MILLIY MADANIY YONDASHUV ASOSIDA TALABALARDA O'QUV TASHABBUSKORLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY-AMALIY ASOSLARI.....	560
<i>Azimova Nilufar Nuriddinovna</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINI TA'MINLASHDA BANK RESURSLARINING ROLI	567
<i>Xodjayeva Jeyrona Ravshonbek qizi</i>	
O'QUV DASTURINI INTEGRATSIYALASH VA YASHIL KO'NIKMALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH: AKADEMIK VA SANOAT O'RTASIDAGI TAFOVUTNI YOPISH	572
<i>Qo'ziqulova Dilfuzaxon Maxammatisaqovna</i>	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND DIGITAL PLATFORMS AS A KEY FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS ENTITIES	580
<i>Rizayeva Nilufar Oblakulovna</i>	

IQTISODIY OLIY TA'LIMDA STRATEGIK INNOVATSIYALAR: YASHIL KO'NIKMALARNI MILLIY VA GLOBAL BARQARORLIK MAQSADLARI BILAN MUVOFIQLASHTIRISH	585
<i>Xasanova Zarina Maxamadaliyevna</i>	
MARKAZIY OSIYODA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT: BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH YO'LIDAGI TO'SIQLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	594
<i>Aminov Shovkat O'ktam o'g'li</i>	
ПЕСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЁНЫХ ОБЛИГАЦИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	598
<i>Саидахмедова Аида Мирзаевна</i>	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ И СНИЖЕНИЕ РИСКОВ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ТРАНЗАКЦИЙ В ФИНАНСОВЫХ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ СИСТЕМАХ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ СИММЕТРИЧНЫХ КРИПТОСИСТЕМ.....	605
<i>Раҳимбердиев Қ.Б.</i>	
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫХ И СТРАХОВЫХ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ДЛЯ СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА	612
<i>Ш.Ф.Кобилжонова</i>	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ КАПИТАЛА ХОЗЯЙСТВУЮЩИХ СУБЪЕКТОВ В КОНТЕКСТЕ РАЗВИТИЯ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА ЭКОНОМИКИ	618
<i>Д.А.Юлдашева</i>	
РОЛЬ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И СТРАХОВЫХ МЕХАНИЗМОВ В СТИМУЛИРОВАНИИ РАЗВИТИЯ ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА	624
<i>Г.Т.Ахмедова</i>	
SUG'URTA BOZORI FAOLIYATINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TRANSFORMATSIYALASH VA UNING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI.....	630
<i>Saidov Farrux Faxriddinovich</i>	
OPPORTUNITIES TO ENSURE SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE ENERGY SECTOR THROUGH THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY.....	635
<i>Ulashov Aliboy Rashid ugli, Istamova Nasiba Narzillo kizi</i>	
INKLYUZIV OLIY TA'LIMDA MUSTAQIL ISHLASH JARAYONINI TASHKILLASHTIRISH.....	641
<i>Akbarova Kamola Abdujabbor qizi</i>	
YOUTH-DRIVEN PATHWAYS TO GREEN EMPLOYMENT: A THEORETICAL EXAMINATION OF INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC STRATEGIES	646
<i>Suvpulatov Ozodjon Alijon ugli</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES INFRATUZILMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR VA UNING O'ZBEKISTON UCHUN AHAMIYATI	651
<i>Botirova Xulkar Olimjonovna</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH KLASTERLARI: NAZARIY ASOSLAR VA AMALIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	655
<i>Sherkulova Nodirabegim Baxordin qizi</i>	
BIOTECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS IN URBAN PLANNING: OPPORTUNITIES AND LIMITATIONS OF "LIQUID TREES"	660
<i>Nosirkulov Asadjon Ahmadjon ugli</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TIKLANADIGAN ENERGIYA MANBALARINING O'RNI.....	663
<i>Fayziyeva Dilso'z Bahodirovna</i>	
KREDIT PORTFELIDA MUAMMOLI KREDITLAR ULUSHINI KAMAYTIRISH YO'LLARI	668
<i>Salixova G.J</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KANDOLAT MAHSULOTLARI BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	672
<i>Boboyorova Maftuna Xaqqul qizi, Boboyorov Islombek Xaqqul o'g'li</i>	
OLIJ TA'LIM TIZIMIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI QO'LLASH METODLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	675
<i>Xusniddinov Yorqinjon Muhiddin o'g'li</i>	

MODA SANOATIDA CRM TIZIMLARINI ELEKTRON SAVDO PLATFORMALARI BILAN UYG'UNLASHTIRISHDAGI TO'SIQLAR	679
Xalilova Nafisa Komilovna	
ENHANCING FOREIGN ECONOMIC RELATIONS AS A DRIVING FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY	683
Khaitova Feruza Bahrom kizi	
MARKAZIY OSIYO MAMLAKATLARIDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNING QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA MANBALARIGA TA'SIRI	687
Akishova Shaxnoza Davlet qizi	
BUXORO VILOYATIDA HUNARMANDCHILIK FAOLIYATINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI: TAHLIL VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	693
Ravshanova Gulchexra Ravshanovna	
SANOATNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING MEXANIZMLARI TURLARI VA OLIMLARNING YONDASHUVLARI	698
Ne'matov Shoxruxbek Ma'murjon o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA KREDIT RISKLARINI BOSHQARISH AMALIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA UNING XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI.....	703
Norova Nozima Nabiyevna	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA REAL SEKTORNI KREDITLASH MEXANIZMLARINI SAMARALI JORIY ETISH VA XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJIGA TA'SIRI.....	709
Abduxomidov Ikromjon Maxamadin o'g'li	
MOLIYA TIZIMIDA BOJ-TARIF SIYOSATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI (OZIQ-OVQAT IMPORTI MISOLIDA).....	715
Rizaev Mirmahmud Xotamjanovich	
YASHIL MARKETING VA ESG INTEGRATSIYASI: STATISTIK TAHLIL VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	721
Charos G'ayratova	
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОГО КАПИТАЛА ДЛЯ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА В УСЛОВИЯХ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ» ЭКОНОМИКИ.....	727
Г.А.Хайитбаева	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH SHAROITIDA TIJORAT BANKLAR TOMONIDAN TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI KREDITLASH.....	734
Tajiddinov Jamshiddin Shamsutdinovich	
IQTISODIYOTNING TARKIBIY TRANSFORMATSIYASIGA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALAR TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	738
Shodiboyeva Dilzoda Farhodjon qizi	
MOLIYA TIZIMI BARQARORLIGI VA BUDJET TUSHUMLARINI OSHIRISHDA TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATNING AHAMIYATI.....	743
Aktamov Akbarjon Aslan o'g'li	
ENSURING SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY: AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CARBON EMISSIONS AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT.....	748
Shakhriddinova Sitara Tolibjon kizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH JARAYONIDA TIJORAT BANKLARIDA INVESTITSIYA LOYIHALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA ESG TAMOYILLARINING ROLI	760
Ostonaqulova Gulchehraxon Muhammadyoqub qizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA SANOAT KORXONALARIDA YETKAZIB BERISH STRATEGIYALARINI ISHLAB CHIQISH	769
Yusupov Ulug'bek Mamayusupovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT KONTEKSTIDA MAKROIQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI MUSTAHKAMLASH: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI.....	776
Isroilov Islomiddin Kamoliddin o'g'li	

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA SPORT TASHKILOTLARINING YANGI BIZNES MODELLARINI ISHLAB CHIQISH	782
G'ulomov Musirmon	
O'ZBEKISTONDA IQTISODIYOTGA XORIJIY INVESTISIYALARNI JALB ETISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	786
Sharipova Shahnoza Baxtiyorovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTISIYA MUHITIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR VA INVESTISIYALARNING IQTISODIYOTGA JALB ETILISH HOLATI TAHLILI	795
Karimova Qunduz Atanazarovna	
O'ZBEKISTON TURISTIK XIZMATLAR BOZORIDA BANDLIK TRANSFORMATSIYASINI VA UNI TARTIBGA SOLISH HOLATINI TAHLIL QILISH	804
To'xtayeva Xurshida Farxodovna	
INVESTITSIYA LOYIHALARIGA TA'SIR QILUVCHI INVESTITSIYA RISKLARINI BAHOLASH.....	811
Zohidova Ruksora Komiljon qizi	
ТИПЫ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ФИНАНСОВЫХ РАЗВЕДОК: ОСНОВНЫЕ РАЗЛИЧИЯ, ФОРМЫ И МЕТОДЫ ОСУЩЕСТВЛЕНИЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	817
Эсанов Шохрух Отабекович	
FACE RECOGNITION PROGRAM IN PYTHON.....	823
Khurramova Maftunakhon Zhurabekovna, Khurramov Azizjon Bakhodir ugli	
FORMATION OF ACCOUNTING POLICY FOR INTANGIBLE ASSETS.....	827
Farxod T. Abdvaxidov, Ramazon A. Abdurakhmanov	
O'ZBEKISTON EKSPORT TARKIBINI YUQORI QO'SHIMCHA QIYMATLI MAHSULOTLARGA O'TKAZISH STRATEGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	834
Raximov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
EKSPORT FAOLIYATIDA ERKIN IQTISODIY ZONALARNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	838
Berdivaliyeva Madina Komiljon qizi	
TURIZM KLASTERLARIDA TIBBIY XIZMATLAR INTEGRATSIYASI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI	841
Yazdanova Shohista Tuyg'un qizi Farxodova Shohnoza Umidbek qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON HAVO TRANSPORTI TIZIMINING JAHON IQTISODIYOTIDAGI O'RNI VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	850
Azimova Moxinur Nozimovna	

STAFF PERFORMANCE EVALUATION BASED ON KPI SYSTEM INDICATORS

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Abstract: This article examines the interrelation between sustainable tourism development and biodiversity protection in Uzbekistan within the framework of UNESCO World Heritage. It explores how cultural and natural heritage sites, recognized by UNESCO, contribute to the promotion of ecotourism and the preservation of unique ecosystems. The study analyzes challenges such as balancing economic benefits from tourism with the need to protect fragile biodiversity, managing visitor flows, and ensuring community participation. Special attention is given to the role of state policies, international cooperation, and local initiatives in fostering sustainable tourism practices that support both cultural heritage and environmental conservation.

Key words: Sustainable tourism; biodiversity protection; Uzbekistan; UNESCO World Heritage; ecotourism; cultural heritage; natural heritage; environmental conservation; community involvement; sustainable development.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda barqaror turizmni rivojlantirish va biologik xilma-xillikni muhofaza qilish o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlik UNESCO Butunjahon merosi doirasida yoritilgan. UNESCO tomonidan e'tirof etilgan madaniy va tabiiy meros obyektlarining ekoturizmni rivojlantirish hamda noyob ekotizimlarni asrashdagi ahamiyati tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, turizm iqtisodiy foydasi va biologik xilma-xillikni muhofaza qilish o'rtasidagi muvozanat, tashrif buyuruvchilar oqimini boshqarish va mahalliy hamjamiyatni jalb etish masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Davlat siyosati, xalqaro hamkorlik va mahalliy tashabbuslarning barqaror turizm amaliyotlarini rivojlantirishdagi roli alohida o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: barqaror turizm; biologik xilma-xillik; O'zbekiston; UNESCO Butunjahon merosi; ekoturizm; madaniy meros; tabiiy meros; ekologik muhofaza; jamoatchilik ishtiroki; barqaror rivojlanish.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается взаимосвязь между развитием устойчивого туризма и охраной биологического разнообразия в Узбекистане в рамках объектов Всемирного наследия ЮНЕСКО. Анализируется роль культурных и природных памятников, признанных ЮНЕСКО, в продвижении экотуризма и сохранении уникальных экосистем. В исследовании изучаются проблемы обеспечения баланса между экономическими выгодами от туризма и необходимостью защиты уязвимого биоразнообразия, управления туристическими потоками и привлечения местных сообществ. Особое внимание уделено роли государственной политики, международного сотрудничества и местных инициатив в развитии практик устойчивого туризма, поддерживающих как культурное наследие, так и охрану окружающей среды.

Ключевые слова: устойчивый туризм; охрана биоразнообразия; Узбекистан; Всемирное наследие ЮНЕСКО; экотуризм; культурное наследие; природное наследие; охрана окружающей среды; участие сообществ; устойчивое развитие.

INTRODUCTION

The level of global innovation development is assessed by various international ratings. These include the Global Innovation Index (GII), Technology Readiness Index (TRI), Information and Communication Technology Index (ICTI), Global Competitiveness Index (GCI), calculated by the World Economic Forum. In these rankings,

countries with high scientific and technical potential, striving to maintain leadership in science, occupy leading positions. Leading enterprises and organizations widely use KPI (Key performance indicator), that is, a system for assessing the main indicator of labor efficiency.

In world practice, the importance of a strategic assessment of labor activity at enterprises is also growing. This is due to the expansion of the competence of the heads of enterprises in the management of human resources, as well as an increase in the level of their responsibility for their economic situation. Improving the system of increasing labor efficiency at the enterprise determines their competitiveness. In this regard, based on the current situation in the global economy, further increasing the income of workers on the basis of a correct, fair and transparent assessment of their work and ensuring their decent work in the workplace is considered an urgent task. Particular attention is paid to research in the direction of assessing the work of employees on the basis of a system for assessing the effectiveness of their work.

In our study, increasing labor efficiency is of great practical importance in developing strategies and tactics for solving issues of ensuring the successful functioning of industrial production enterprises. Improving labor efficiency is currently the most important socio-economic problem. Before analyzing the concept of labor efficiency, it is important to understand the essence of the concepts of effect and efficiency. The concepts of "effect" and "efficiency" are interpreted as large-scale, nationwide categories and include scientific, technical, social, economic and other results. The concept of "effect" - if analyzed from an economic point of view - means saving or reducing production resources when creating products, goods or services. "Effect" - in general terms, is the difference between the result and the costs, between the planned (target) and current (actual) indicators.

The results of the study showed that the "effect", "result" by their nature are expressed in quantitative and qualitative indicators. Quantitative indicators are expressed in absolute terms, i.e. in units of cost, natural and conditional measurement, while qualitative indicators can be used in various comparative, i.e. relative indicators. In the economic literature, concepts related to the essence of efficiency are classified on the basis of various criteria and indicators.

The purpose of this article is to propose typical quality indicators aimed at maximizing the development of the personality of employees and at the same time improving the system for assessing important indicators of labor efficiency in enterprises.

The novelty of the approach lies in the formation of a universal model of the main indicators of the system for assessing important indicators of labor efficiency, which can be used by most enterprises in the implementation of their strategies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Most authors believe that efficiency is a relative indicator and that it is determined through the ratio of costs to the obtained (achieved) result [1].

On the issues of efficiency, a number of scientific studies were carried out by scientists from far abroad and CIS countries, who expressed their views. Modern Western economists D.L. Gibson, D.M. Ivantsevich and D.H. Donnelly analyzed the concept of "efficiency" in three directions: firstly, as the level of achievement of the goals of the enterprise (organization), secondly, as the level of coordination of interests, and thirdly, as the level of survival, habituation, flexibility in the external environment" [2].

The concept of "efficiency" was interpreted by the Italian economist Wilfred Pareto as follows: "efficiency is the achievement of high results in a production system without compromising any process" [3].

V.V. Novozhilov expresses efficiency as follows: "efficiency is expressed in general form in the ratio of the beneficial effect (efficiency) to the costs of obtaining it. The efficiency indicator in the following cases is expressed in inverse form, i.e. in the ratio of costs to efficiency" [four].

L.M. Chistov gives the following definition of the concept of "efficiency": "efficiency is the concentration of useful properties in the form of a product produced at the expense of a unit of resources used per unit of time" [5]. It also showed several performance indicators with the same content: qualitative indicators of resource productivity, intensive functioning of the socio-economic system and gross use of resources. It determines the resource return indicator by dividing the unit of capacity of objects of gross use of resources by the unit of return of the used average annual gross resources [6].

A.V. Karpov believes that "efficiency is, first of all, a concept that characterizes the qualitative aspects of an enterprise's activities. He proceeds from the category "effect", describes that efficiency is more complex and complex than effect. Efficiency as an indicator in advance determines many technical, economic, design and economic decisions. The enterprise proceeds from efficiency in determining its economic, scientific, technical and investment policy" [7].

The American scientist-economist D. Sink gives different definitions of the meaning of the word "efficiency": «1. Efficiency - from English, means low costs, efficiency, expresses the necessary and practical costs of

resources. 2. Effectiveness - from English, expresses the relationship of quality 3. Productivity - from English, denotes productivity, performance (the ratio of the volume of output to the costs of available resources). 4. Profitability - from English, utility. 5. Innovation - innovation. 6. Quality of labor life is a quality labor activity»[8]. Colens' dictionary notes that «efficiency» is manifested in low-cost factors and intermediate relations in the production of goods and services [9].

As is known, private indicators characterizing economic efficiency at enterprises include indicators of the use of labor resources, indicators of the effective use of material and financial resources. Of particular importance are indicators of the efficiency of the use of available labor resources.

N. Bereza defines KPI as a set of indicators for evaluating the performance of employees. The author limits the scope of application of the main performance indicators to the area of personnel management [10].

A. Gavrilyuk defines the concept of «significant performance indicator» as a coefficient characterizing the degree of achievement of the goal [11].

V. Petrova, based on the analysis of the meaning of the word in the abbreviation KPI, indicates that this term should be interpreted as the main indicators[12].

T. Lobanova defines KPI as information that allows you to evaluate the work of employees [13].

L. Rudenko, N. Degtyar define the concept of «the most important performance indicators» as a system of financial and non-financial indicators that characterize the result of achieving the strategic and tactical goals of the enterprise [14].

Leading scientists of our country also put forward their views on the problem of efficiency. In particular, the academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan K.Kh.

A. Ulmasov, A. Vakhobov interpret this concept as follows: «Efficiency means comparing the result obtained from production with the consumption of resources, that is, it shows what was achieved at what expense» [16].

K.Zh. Mirzaev, M.K. Pardaev define this concept as follows: «Efficiency is understood as a set of economic relations between such entities as society, the state, the owner, the enterprise, the owner of the labor force, aimed at ensuring the commonality of their interests through the effective use of all available resources and ensure cost savings, regardless of the form of ownership» [17].

M.K.Pardaev, B.A. Abduraimov, give the following definition: «Efficiency - shows with what result the ongoing economic process will end» [18]. In this definition, the concept of efficiency is approached from an economic point of view and the concept arose that efficiency arises only in the economic process. In our opinion, efficiency is not only the final state of the economic process, but also the achieved level of social result. Recognizing that the concept of efficiency is a complex concept that has several translational interpretations in the scientific literature (efficiency - eng.) (efficientia - lat.), the somewhat common word «efficiency» can be expressed in terms of such concepts as efficiency, productivity, mobility and efficiency [19]. Currently, many definitions of efficiency are presented not only in economic sciences, but also in other sciences.

In economic sciences, the concept of «efficiency» is interpreted in a narrow and broad sense. The concept of «efficiency» in the narrow sense: is a complex classification of the result of potential and actual activities, which focuses on the results obtained as a result of activities. In a broad sense, the concept of «efficiency» is interpreted as: the ability to effectively and adequately approach the environment [20], relative effect, operations and projects, rational use of consumed resources.

Determining and improving the efficiency of labor activity remains the most important task in the current conditions of economic development. One of the priority tasks today is to improve the system for attracting the most modern equipment and technologies for enterprises in Uzbekistan, creating jobs, maintaining existing ones, assessing critical indicators of labor efficiency at the enterprise based on the system of training and development of its employees. Therefore, studies conducted to assess important indicators of labor efficiency in the enterprise are of great importance.

This dissertation research, to a certain extent, serves to implement the tasks noted in the Decrees and Resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 24, 2017 No. PD-5052 "On measures to further improve the state policy in the field of employment and radically increase the efficiency of labor bodies", dated 21 November 2018 No. PD-4022 «On measures to further modernize the digital infrastructure in order to develop the digital economy», dated October 31, 2019 No. PD-4503 «On measures to improve the training system in the banking and financial sector», dated January 24, 2022 No. PD-99 «On measures to create an effective system for the development of production and expansion of industrial cooperation in the Republic», Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 1, 2021 No. 410 "On measures to improve the efficiency of labor activity of citizens employed in temporary, seasonal and one-time work", as well as in other regulatory legal acts related to this area.

To assess the effectiveness of labor, its multidimensionality as a socio-economic category, a certain system of indicators is required. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the different levels of determining labor efficiency depending on the scale of production (sectors of the economy, sphere, enterprise, workshop, site,

team). On top of that, even at the same level - at the level of certain enterprises (industries, workshops) - the systems of indicators may differ, since production volumes are calculated differently, the composition of personnel (skill level, work experience, number) is different and there will be their own accounting features labor costs.

To date, among economists there is no consensus on the method of assessing the effectiveness of labor in the industrial production sector. Many economists argue that the concepts of «labor productivity» and «labor efficiency» are similar concepts. For example, V.I. Ivanitsky, I.N. Maksimenko and N.N. Ushakova [23] give the following definition: «labor efficiency is characterized by labor productivity associated with a decrease or increase in labor costs for the volume of work performed». This idea was also noted by I.I. Volkov [24] in his research work. There are also inaccuracies on the part of the scientists of our country, for example, in the textbook by A. Ulmasov and A. Vakhobov «Theory of Economics» it is recognized that: «Labor productivity means the result of labor, labor efficiency» [25].

Labor efficiency, in contrast to labor productivity, is not only the volume of labor, but also its quality. The quality of work should be considered in two senses. In a narrow sense, it expresses the quality of products, in a broad sense - social utility, compliance of labor results with established requirements. Another important aspect of labor efficiency is that it expresses, in turn, savings in the use of labor resources, the labor intensity of human labor activity in the field of material and non-material production. The table provides a classification of these mutually exclusive aspects into categories that differ from each other in the degree of economic use.

Table 1. The difference between labor efficiency and labor productivity and production efficiency

Distinctive Aspects	Production efficiency	Labor productivity	Labor efficiency
Sphere of work	Production of wealth	Labor in the sphere of material production	Gross useful labor (material and non-material production)
Influence on the mass of created material values and services	Increasing the efficiency of production leads to an increase in the required material values to meet savings and current needs.	The growth of labor productivity increases all the material values of society	An increase in labor efficiency leads to an increase in the mass of services along with material values

V.V. Novozhilov made a great contribution to the popularization of labor efficiency as an economic category, according to which «... the useful properties of a product do not depend on its quantity. The product may be useful or unnecessary, necessary or superfluous. volume of the labor force, but this negatively affects its efficiency»[26] . Therefore, labor efficiency is considered a much broader concept than the concept of production. Labor efficiency in itself not only reflects the quantity of the product, but also expresses the consumer value of the product, as well as the effect of labor in the sectors of the economy. Labor efficiency is one of the most important economic categories that characterize the socio-economic development of the country and enterprises. Labor efficiency as an economic category in essence and content can be analyzed in 3 directions: the first direction - the subject of research is the economic efficiency of labor or production itself. The role of this economic category in the system of economic sciences is great, it explores the interaction of labor efficiency with objective economic laws, and this economic category is of interest to many scientists with its specificity in various forms of production; the second direction is connected with the search for criteria for labor productivity and its quantitative norms, as well as performance indicators at various levels of the economy, with the study of the dynamics of efficiency; and the third direction is connected with the study of special influencing factors, as well as ways and reserves to increase labor efficiency through their economic sphere.

Table 2. Classification of indicators for measuring the performance of an enterprise [27]

Efficiency		Performance
Production	Work	Labor productivity
The ratio of the volume of GDP or the final product to one unit of material, labor and financial resources	The ratio of the volume of GDP created to labor costs and quality in sectors of the economy	The ratio of GDP produced to the total number of people employed in the sphere of material production

At the mesolevel		
The degree to which an industry's gross requirements are satisfied for a particular product. The ratio of the amount of produced or net product in kind to each unit of all resources used	The ratio of net product to the labor intensity and quality of labor in the industry	The ratio of the normative net product produced in the industry to the total number of personnel in the industrial manufacturing industry
At the micro level		
Indicators of provision, labor productivity, capital productivity, production capacity, prime cost, plan fulfillment, profitability	The ratio of the created net product and produced material values (with qualitative indicators) to the saved working time and living labor	The ratio of the volume of net product to each worker in industrial production or the ratio of labor costs per unit of output

These 3 areas are also inextricably linked, and their main goal is to theoretically substantiate labor efficiency. The study of the essence of labor efficiency should first of all begin with determining which industry it belongs to: whether it belongs to the sphere of material production or to the sphere of non-material production.

Insufficient use of labor resources at industrial production enterprises (a discrepancy between the real and potential capabilities of an employee and their implementation) is manifested in a discrepancy between the needs of production and the professional composition of workers-employees, in a discrepancy between the existing and actually necessary level of qualification of workers-employees, in the irrational distribution of labor functions, in dissatisfaction with work, its organization and conditions, in the insufficient development of a sense of responsibility of workers-employees.

These factors directly affect the efficiency of the use of labor resources at industrial enterprises, the quality of output and, as a result, lead to a decrease in labor productivity. As a factor in increasing the efficiency of labor in industrial enterprises, direct labor resources and their effective use are associated with a combination of quantitative and qualitative indicators of workers and employees, as well as their effective use.

The importance of incentives in managing employee turnover is great. While the effect of incentives on employee turnover has been extensively studied in the literature, the bulk of the research in this area will focus on the tangible or non-tangible aspects of incentives. Separately, it should be noted that the study of the role of the KPI system in the relationship between material incentives and staff turnover has not been conducted.

Research shows that financial incentives are an important factor in motivating employees. However, staff turnover is a process that occurs as a result of a violation of the principles of fairness in management and material incentives.

Today there is an understanding that the KPI system can serve as an important basis for the introduction of material and non-material incentives for employees on the principles of justice. However, there is also a partial influence of family values, social, religious and secular views of the staff.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology is based on empirical data obtained during the development of the KPI system for assessing the most important performance indicators of enterprises with structure.

The basis is Decrees and Resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, data from the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations and other relevant regulatory legal acts.

The study used the methods of system analysis, comparative analysis, correlation and regression analysis, forecasting.

The study used data from a survey of 1,130 employees working at such industrial enterprises as Shaxrisabz VAOT Joint-Stock Company, DON-XALQ RIZQI Joint-Stock Company, OQ SAROY TEXTILE LLC and SADO LLC operating in the Kashkadarya region. The expected relationships are estimated using the least squares structural equation modeling method. The results showed that material incentives, training and staff development are positively correlated with the KPI system, which, in turn, is negatively correlated with staff turnover. The indirect effect of incentives on staff turnover is supported only for material incentives, training and staff development, since it should be analyzed whether there is a relationship between properly organized labor and fair management, as well as non-material incentives with the KPI system.

In our study, the results are obtained by simultaneously examining the role of two types of incentives in the «work» of the KPI system and, in turn, employee turnover. After testing a model that includes financial and

non-financial incentives, as part of our study, when explaining the KPI system, we studied whether financial incentives have additional predictive power in relation to non-financial incentives.

Separately, it can be noted that if, based on the KPI system, incentives indicate that the employee is worthy of the organization, the work of employees is fairly encouraged, then the motivation of employees to work reduces staff turnover.

Thus, the following hypotheses were considered appropriate:

1. The relationship between financial incentives and staff turnover is implemented through the KPI system.
2. Non-material incentives, that is, the relationship between properly organized labor and fair management, the system of training and advanced training of employees and staff turnover is carried out through the KPI system.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The survey data of 1130 employees working at industrial enterprises of the Kashkadarya region were used effectively, the result was very good, the response rate was 84.16% (951 people). The study analysis included 69% male and 31% female participants. Participants were 32.5 years old on average (minimum = 22 years; maximum = 56 years). 52.4 percent of participants have a master's degree, while 45.6 percent have a bachelor's degree. The majority of participants (79.8%) have worked in their current organization for between one and ten years, 17.2% have worked there between 11 and 20 years, and only 3% have more than 21 years of service.

The survey questions were formulated with the participation of employers, their representatives and specialists. Responses were scored on a 5-point scale, with 1 and 5 meaning «strongly disagree» and «strongly agree» respectively. The study took into account the age, gender, length of service, education and occupation of the respondents.

The analysis of the study was carried out using the SmartPLS program. SmartPLS is a least squares trajectory modeling technique that simultaneously tests the relationship between measurement metrics and their latent structures, as well as the structural model, i.e. the relationship between structures. Of course, it's worth noting that PLS is very useful for model evaluation if the sample size is small and the model is complex.

The study evaluated the reliability, consistency of individual elements and the authenticity of the discriminant. We used a minimum level of 0.05 to receive weights. Two questions on training and professional development of personnel, as well as one on employee turnover and on the KPI system were not used in further analysis, since the questions had a negative weight.

Table 3. Weight, reliability and mean variance of the factors obtained from the results of the study

Factors	CR	AVE	Bec
Training and professional development of employees	0.797	0.663	0.842
Properly organized labor and fair management	0.749	0.611	0.625
Financial incentive	0.848	0.589	0.649
KPI system	0.881	0.644	0.728
Non-financial incentives	0.871	0.621	0.661
Staff turnover	0.919	0.851	0.891
			0.949

Where: CR – composite reliability; AVE – average variance

For all other indicators, the weight coefficients showed an indicator above 0.625, which indicates a reliable relationship between the indicators and their respective factors. In addition, all safety factors (CR) were above 0.7, indicating sufficient internal consistency of measures. To assess the reliability of convergent and discriminant indicators, the Fornell and Larsker test was used. Convergent authenticity is confirmed if the issued mean deviation (Ave) is greater than 0.50. For all factors, the mean variance (Ave) was above 0.5, which determines the convergent validity of latent factors.

Table 4. Discriminant reliability coefficients obtained during the study

Factors	1	2	3	4	5	6
Employee training and development (1)	0.817					
Properly organized work and fair management (2)	0.204	0.779				
Financial incentives (3)	0.141	0.279	0.768			
KPI system (4)	0.379	0.371	0.539	0.811		
Non-financial incentives (5)	0.474	0.482	0.463	0.478	0.786	
Staff turnover (6)	-0.172	-0.216	0.304	-0.393	-0.418	0.922

We collected data from respondents using a one-time survey, which may lead to a general discrepancy in the potential method. Interpretive factor analysis showed that the largest factor showed only 28.5% of the variance, indicating no problems in the study data related to general differences in methods.

Table 5. Path- coefficients, impact size and dispersion

Criterion	Factors	β	t- meaning	Scope of Influence	VIF
Staff turnover R2 = 0,185	KPI system	-0.411	4.890***	0.181	1.644
KPI system R = .0459	Training and professional development of employees	0.256	2.639**	0.086	1.625
	Properly organized labor and fair management	0.181	1.648	0.043	1.401
	Non-financial incentives	0.067	0.499	0.006	1.951
	Financial incentive	0.439	4.229***	0.248	1.361

Where: β , beta; VIF (variance inflation factor); *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$.

The importance of Path coefficients was assessed using bootstrap analysis in SmartPLS3. Figure 1 shows the path estimates of the main structural direct impact of the model between latent variables. Table 5 lists Path coefficients, t-values, impact size, and VIF variance scores.

The results of the internal evaluation of the model showed 46.5% changes in the KPI system and 18.6% in staff turnover. Of the 46.5% discrepancies in the KPI system, 13.1% corresponded only to the share of financial incentives, which indicates a higher level of financial incentives in the study of the KPI system than non-financial incentives. In addition, the Path scores showed that only two of the four proposals regarding the impact of incentives on the KPI system were supported.

Fig.1. SEM Model Estimation

To confirm the first hypothesis, we found a significant positive relationship between material incentives and the KPI system ($\beta = 0.439$; $p < 0.001$). Contrary to our expectations, the assessment of the system model showed that the relationship between well organized work and fair management with the KPI system was not significant ($\beta = 0.181$; $p = 0.099$). The results of the analysis showed that the positive effect of training and staff development on the KPI system is maintained ($\beta = 0.256$, $p < 0.05$), while the effect of non-material incentives on the KPI system is not supported ($\beta = 0.067$; $p = 0.619$). The study also showed that the KPI system affects employee turnover. The analysis data confirm this relationship ($\beta = -0.411$, $p < 0.001$).

The study shows that material and non-material incentives indirectly affect staff turnover through the KPI system (hypotheses 1 and 2). The results show that financial incentives have an important relationship with the KPI system, which, in turn, is an important predictor of employee turnover. Similarly, training and development of staff indirectly affects employee turnover, since employee turnover is an important predictor of the KPI system, which, in turn, has a significant negative relationship with employee turnover.

Table 6. The results of the indirect influence of the KPI system and staff turnover on other factors

Relationship between factors	β indirect effect	<i>t</i> - meaning	Reliability range (2.5–97.5%)
Employee training and development - KPI system - staff turnover	-0.107	2.51*	(-0.128; -0.021)
Financial incentives - KPI system - staff turnover	-0.176	3.29**	(-0.290; -0073)

Where: ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

Bootstrapping scores showed an indirect effect of incentives and employee training and development on employee turnover ($\beta = -0.176$; $p < 0.01$; $\beta = -0.107$; $p < 0.05$). The model did not support the intermediate effect for well-organized work and fair management, as well as for the relationship from non-monetary incentives for staff turnover, since these two factors are not directly related to the KPI system. Thus, the data support hypothesis 1, partially support hypothesis 2.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In achieving the main goal of assessing the work of employees of an enterprise, a system for assessing the quality of work is important. The quality of labor is a complex economic category that expresses labor relations in the processes of production, distribution, circulation and consumption in a material form while creating consumer value, quantity and quality of goods.

Employees of the enterprise are used to determine the goals within the framework of the Labor Quality Assessment System:

- study of the employee's personal capabilities;
- improving their professional skills by supporting employees through education and training;
- career advancement from professional positions and job changes;
- organization of additional payments and bonuses;
- identification of employees who are not able to meet the production requirements of the enterprise.

As a rule, a number of indicators (requirements) are used in the system for assessing the quality of work. The use of a large number of indicators complicates the work of the calculation, as well as its application in practice. It is advisable that these indicators be easily perceived by workers and be as universal as possible, taking into account workers of all types of work. But at the same time, it is also necessary to take into account that they specialize in a particular type of activity. It should also be noted that some constant requirements have been adopted by many enterprises: these are skill and initiative, constancy in work activity (continuity in work activity), strict dedication in work process, possession of several professional skills, rationalization, ingenuity, etc. At the same time, such requirements as adaptation to the conditions, cooperation, reliability, caution, best practices, the correct attitude to the means of work, full knowledge of one's work, and observance of technical safety rules are also important.

The establishment of such indicators and requirements in the production process of the enterprise is carried out taking into account the psychological and physiological capabilities of workers, mathematical statistics and a number of other factors.

In our study, based on the analysis of the system of important performance indicators (KPI) and staff turnover, which are used in assessing the effectiveness of employees in enterprises, as well as the situation of stimulating employees, fair management and organized work, the following conclusions were drawn:

Firstly, the presence of errors in the choice of certain weight units when implementing a system of important performance indicators (KPI) in an enterprise can lead to staff turnover.

Secondly, when evaluating the effectiveness of labor in the activities of an enterprise, it is advisable to constantly follow the principle of justice, correctly evaluate the activities of the team while stimulating collective and managerial personnel.

Thirdly, the system of important performance indicators (KPI) is an important indicator that shows whether employees are put in their place in any enterprise or not. Therefore, we believe that it is advisable to review the personnel management system of any enterprise before using this system. This is evident from the results given by respondents to survey questions during the study.

Fourthly, the system of important performance indicators (KPI) may not be compatible with the activities of all enterprises where it is recommended to use the system of goals and main results of performance evaluation (OKR, Objectives and Key Results).

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